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MPM4CPS Survey

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Understanding the Nature of Multi-Paradigm Modeling for Cyberphysical Systems

Keywords: Cyberphysical systems, multi-paradigm modeling, tool chaining

Abstract: Cyberphysical systems (CPS) encompass embedded computation with network monitoring that is controlled by physical processes. CPS integrates computational and physical capabilities that allow for interaction with humans through diverse means. Such novel interaction ways expand the capabilities of humans in correlation with the physical world through computation, communication, and control as a key attraction feature of CPS. The thereby created feedback loops from computations affect physical processes and vice versa. The uptake of CPS by industry increases in diverse domains such as avionics, logistics, production smart cities, and so on. To be holistic in CPS design, a profound understanding of the respective elements, their features and their relationships are important. Important for CPS design is the modeling of these elements and their relationships in diverse CPS paradigms. The challenge is to find the most appropriate ways of chaining modeling techniques of diverse paradigms so that a holistic design process is complete, flexible and coherent. This paper fills the gap in an empirical study that investigates the current CPS design practice in industry. The results of the study (we will run the survey in early 2017) indicate what the current best practices are for different domains. Additionally, the results also show existing gaps in multi-paradigm modeling for CPS, which indicates feasible new research directions for tool-chain development.

1 Introduction

There is a clear need to bring different solutions from different technology and application domains together for a holistic design of cyberphysical systems (CPS) (Ragunathan et al., 2010). CPS integrates computational and physical capabilities that allow for interaction with humans through diverse means (Baheti and Gill, 2011). Such novel interaction ways expand the capabilities of humans in correlation with the physical world through computation, communication, and control as a key attraction feature of CPS. For example, in domains in the design and development of next-generation avionics and vehicles, smart cities, Industry 4.0, and so on. A specific challenge in CPS for a holistic system design is to reconcile many model types belonging to different perspectives (Derler et al., 2012). For example, hybrid system modeling and simulation, concurrent and heterogeneous models of computation, using domain-specific ontologies modularity enhancement, etc. The multi-paradigm modeling (MPM) perspective advocates modeling every part and aspect of a problem explicitly, using the most appropriate formalisms and abstractions, with explicitly modeled processes.

Based on the described status quo, the problem statement of this empirical research paper is that the uptake of multi-paradigm modeling for cyberphysical systems is not sufficiently given due to

lacking awareness and also a lack of existing solutions. Thus, we adopt a set of research objectives starting with the exploration of challenges that practitioners perceive in MPM for CPS. It is also important to understand the existing categories of problems and benefits in the application of existing solutions. Affiliated with the objective of finding viable business cases and best practices, we try to detect the existing level of understanding about MPM for CPS and finally also communicate a shared understanding.

The context of this practitioner-oriented empirical research targets stakeholders in CPS development such as engineers, chief executives, projects managers and customers who are involved in a European COST Action for multi-paradigm modeling of cyberphysical systems¹. More concretely, we investigate the state of the art of models used for CPS design. Those models must be analyzable, well founded and supported by tool sets that support best-practice activities and interoperabilities between tools. The modeling activities are part of multi-paradigm CPS-design methods and techniques involving diverse sets of languages. With respect to CPS-design methods, we investigate the entire lifecycle from initial requirements harvesting to the further stages of specification, integration, verification, implementation, maintenance, and so on. The motivation for settling on this given investigation context is that we aim to gain a deeper complexity understanding of MPM for CPS to identify existing research- and development needs that yield improvements in this domain.

The planned remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 discusses related work by presenting earlier studies and related theories. Section 3 gives the casestudy design comprising of research questions, the concrete cases and subjects selection with data-collection procedures together with their analysis and validation. Next, Section 4 shows a survey beta-version that requires testing before an alpha version is released.

2 Related Work

For the related work of addressing the intersection of CPS and MPM, we give separate corresponding sections and discuss related work in an order based on their publication year so that trends are revealed. First, Section 2.1 comprises related work for CPS and Section 2.2 for MPM.

2.1 CPS Related Work

A survey in (Shi et al., 2011) states that CPS closely integrates cyber- and physical elements while the latter has resource constraints. The networking between the multiple CPS must scale extremely from a temporal and spatial perspective. Reorganizations and reconfigurations happen dynamically in a system with high degree of automation where loops are closed and must be dependable. Typical research directions address energy control, cyber-security control, communication transmission and management, and modelbased software design. Typical CPS applications are healthcare and medicine, electric power grid, and intelligent roads for unmanned vehicles. The detected research

¹ <http://mpm4cps.eu/>

directions are control of hybrid systems, sensors and mobile networks, robustness, reliability, safety and security, model-based abstractions and their verification, validation and certification.

The authors of (Teodora and Liviu, 2012) consider CPS to be an integration of computation with physical processes and thus, is about intersection, not the union of the physical and the cyber and assume otherwise the same characteristics as in (Shi et al., 2011). The understanding of CPS is now evolved to the application purpose of learning, adaptation, enhanced system performance, self-organization that also comprises auto-assembly. The main CPS features are secured communication channels, a federated design, real-time performance, geographic distribution with an orchestration and choreography by a system-of-systems element involved. The authors see as application domains for CPS critical infrastructure control, safe and efficient transport, alternative energy management, environmental control, telepresence, medical devices and integrated systems for telemedicine and assisted living, manufacturing, agriculture and social networking with gaming.

In (Schatz et al., 2013), CPS is a disruptive change for the economy and society at large. As a science, CPS integrates multiple paradigms of a sociotechnical nature for achieving a collaboration between humans and smart objects that interact following common system theory. The paper lists CPS challenges that occur in diverse domains. First, technological CPS challenges pertain to upscaling engineering methods for handling the occurring complexity. The latter involve managing global-scale mission-critical processes that reach across borders. These processes can not be turned off but must instead be changed at runtime. To support the processes, the need occurs for methods, tools and platforms that support interoperability with maturing autonomous behavior where the privacy of uncertain information is assured in a dependable way. Examples of relevant CPS technology are embedded systems, mechatronics, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data and system of systems (SoS). The economy is affected by CPS in that new business models emerge characterized by new value networks. Consequently a shift occurs from products towards service-orientation. The sociotechnical nature of CPS is stressed by additional societal, educational and legal challenges. Society may react in a very risk-averse way to such disruptive technology. As a counter measure the public should be educated for gathering support towards CPS innovation. Consequently, novel education- and training programs must be established that balance theory and practice so that a knowledge transfer also happens to key stakeholders in society. Finally, it is also important to eliminate legal innovation barriers that block CPS diffusion in society. Ideally, we see a Europe-wide harmonization for eliminating unclear legal interpretations and improving Europe-wide accepted CPS-certifications.

As the reference above also mentions, security is a specific CPS topic and a focus in (Shafi, 2012). The main quality goals that must be assured are confidentiality, integrity, availability, and authenticity. As such, a CPS must secure sensing, data storage, communication, action control and feedback provision. Thus, it is important to mitigate, detect and prevent, e.g., eavesdropping, spoofing, and attacks via compromised keys, men in the middle, or denial of service.

The ideal means for enabling CPS is the support by a Cloud environment. According to (Reddy, 2014), this again raises security-related issues such as managing and controlling access rights to

sensitive data, developing attack-detection models. Thus, since a Cloud platform for the “cyber” part in CPS is critical, it is important to have a strong security architecture for a Cloud involving fault-tolerance management, dedicated security windows for respective entities and corresponding enforcement levels. This raises interested security challenges such as enhancing the reliability, safety, privacy and security of CPS against environment attacks and natural disasters that establish trust, new paradigm for real-time resource management such as smart objects. This also means there a lack of understanding the notion of quality of service in a heterogeneous and hybrid CPS environment.

A very rich application case for CPS is e-healthcare (Haque et al., 2014) where the strengths of the former can be exploited in an optimal way. The given advantages of CPS are scalable heterogeneous network integration that allows real-time interaction between humans and systems involving instant feedback with the help of autonomously acting smart objects that integrate with Clouds. The e-healthcare taxonomy is rather rich and involves several aspects that also hold for other CPS-application domains. First, the taxonomy addresses notable CPS application such as electronic medical records, security, big data and smart checklists. Next, daily living applications comprise domains such as ambient-intelligence compliant objects, wireless identification and sensing, real-time Parkinson monitoring, fall-detection systems, posture analysis applications. Medical status monitoring usually gathers data from wearable biomedical sensors checking heart and pulse rate, oxygen saturation using mobile phones as base stations. Furthermore, medical-intake applications record the removal of pills by breaking an electric flow into the RFID circuit and also involves remote medication intake monitoring and vital signs monitoring. The detected challenges and issues for CPS in e-healthcare are more generally a lack of standards, missing verification and validation tools, sound time management and suitable CPS architectures. Specific e-healthcare CPS challenges are software reliability, medical-device interoperability, security and privacy, system-feedback management, complex query processing.

Finally, in (Thompson et al., 2015) the authors address future CPS challenges. The main findings of challenges points out that CPS are large and often spatially distributed physical systems with complex dynamics for which the control, management and supervision is highly distributed. Adding to the complexity is the partial autonomy of subsystems such as flocks of smart objects that are part of an orchestrated CPS mission. When the latter requires adjustment, the consequence is a dynamic reconfiguration of the overall system on different time-scales requiring a continuous evolution of the overall system during its operation that drives emerging CPS behavior.

2.2 MPM Related Work

Modeling all paradigms of a CPS coherently is a challenging task and we sum up the state of the art. In a study about MPM in the automobile industry (Broy et al., 2013), the finding is that models are used for a generic purpose in projects that are agile and small, where team members have a formal education. Notable effects of model-driven design (MDD) for embedded systems are the improvement in the software quality with a consistent enforcement of structures and architectures.

The most significant observed advancements are a drastic increase in functional correctness and cut in development time while also the system quality improves slightly. However, the tool support is immature and triggers productivity loss as the former is not coherent with MDD, which also incurs a high redesign cost. More specifically, the tools do not support round-trip engineering, model verification, validation and synchronization. Besides saving time and cutting costs. the reason for using MDD is to develop functions of high complexity. MDD application incurs a front loading of activities in a system-design process while a high degree of generated code and testing instances is the outcome. The prerequisite is a high education level of employees who know how to take advantage of the seamless MDD process for generating highly innovative and secure functions.

A survey and exploration of industry cases about model-driven engineering (MDE) in (Hutchinson et al., 2014) shows that most use models for understanding a problem at a higher abstraction level, to enhance team communication and document design decisions for code generation while it is seldom that executable models in domain-specific languages (DSL) serve for testing in concrete simulations. Most survey respondents use UML while less than half employ a DSL and a quarter consider business-process modeling languages. Consequently, the concretely used model types are in the following order class-, activity-, use case- and state diagrams. The perceived effect of MDE is that a significant need emerges for additionally training employees. Consequently by far less skilled. The ability to generate code automatically is perceived as a MDE benefit. The opinion of respondents is split on the issues of how challenging it is to integrate automatically generated code while slightly more respondents think UML is too complex and sufficiently powerful for MDE. Positive for the latter is also that most state MDE promotes an enhanced understanding among stakeholders without resulting in unexpected confusion or misunderstandings. Instead, MDE helps a lot to improve productivity, problem solving, creativity and enjoyment. With respect to observed MDE industry cases in (Hutchinson et al., 2014), the lessons learned for MDE introduction in a printer-, car-, telecom- and defense company reveals that it is beneficial to be organizationally adaptive, business led, committed iterative and progressive while MDE introduction is problematic when the response of an organization is to be rigid, technology led, not committed, autocratic and wholesale.

Finally, a more recent study in (Whittle et al., 2014) confirms too that MDE increases employee training costs and triggers considerable organizational change that leads to a quarter percentage increase in productivity. The noted MDE benefits are the documentation of an explicitly developed good software architecture without a lengthy architecture-definition process that divides simple from complex aspects. That way new value-added business models are attainable where architects are reinforced and coders threatened. The changes are perceived as a threat by the middle management and coders too since the latter require considerable retraining because of their lacking abstraction capabilities. MDE experts themselves must possess multiple-domain knowledge in companies that work on rather specific problems. MDE is not equally suitable for general SW-companies where technology knowledge is favored over domain knowledge. A negative effect of MDE may be that

the architects make models deliberately complex and as simple architectures are perceived as not well thought through.

3 Case Study Design

We developed a first version of a survey that requires first beta-testing before a final version of the survey can be issued with an online survey tool. Our focus group is palled to be pan-European and the results will be reported in a journal paper. The following pages list various sets of of survey questions.

3.1 Research Questions

The main research questions is: How to use MPM for an effective and efficient design of CPS where humans are part the control loop?

Deduced sub-research questions are:

sub rq1: How to study the influence of MPM at respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle?

sub rq1.1: What are the typical lifecycle stages in real-life CPS projects?

sub rq1.2: What are the respective modelling paradigms considered in CPS projects?

sub rq1.3: What paradigms affect respective lifecycle stages in a CPS project?

sub rq2: How to find the key criteria that allow for measuring the benefits of MPM4CPS?

sub rq2.1: What are the criteria that determine the degree of MPM-effectiveness in a CPS project?

sub rq2.2: What are the criteria that determine the degree of MPM-efficiency in a CPS project?

sub rq2.3: What is perceived quality improvement of MPM4CPS?

sub rq3: How to detect the roles that diverse stakeholders play at different stages of an MPM4CPS development lifecycle?

sub rq3.1: What stakeholders roles exist in MPM4CPS?

sub rq3.2: What are the characteristics of those respective stakeholder roles?

sub rq3.3: What stakeholders are involved at respective stages of MPM4CPS?

The propositions below are deduced from the research questions:

rq1 affiliated:

IF a CPS is developed THEN the development lifecycle stages employ modeling techniques and -tools.

IF model-driven engineering is used for CPS-development THEN a diverse spectrum of system paradigms are covered.

IF diverse modelling paradigms are considered for CPS-development THEN all perceived stages of the development lifecycle are affected in a specific way.

rq2 affiliated:

IF MPM is used for CPS development THEN criteria exist that allow for measuring the development effectiveness at respective lifecycle stages.

IF MPM is used for CPS development THEN criteria exist that allow for measuring the development efficiency at respective lifecycle stages.

IF MPM is used for CPS development THEN criteria exist that allow for measuring the quality improvements at respective lifecycle stages.

rq3 affiliated:

IF the stakeholders in MPM4CPS are known THEN they can be abstracted into role definitions.

IF the stakeholders are known THEN it is possible to find a set a characteristics that allow for specifying the features of these respective stakeholders.

IF diverse stakeholders exist in MPM-driven CPS-development THEN it is possible to assign them to respective stages of the development lifecycle.

The propositions above serve as a bridge for the generation of hypotheses that we list below:

rq1 affiliated:

The MPM tools and techniques can be clearly assigned to respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle.

The modeling tools and techniques for CPS-development take into account the complete set of required system paradigms.

The effects of addressing a specific system paradigm with model-based engineering are measurable for respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle.

rq2 affiliated:

The complete set of effectiveness-measuring criteria are known for MPM4CPS.

The complete set of efficiency-measuring criteria are known for MPM4CPS.

All relationships can be fully specified that exist between effectiveness- and efficiency measurement criteria for MPM4CPS.

rq3 affiliated:

All abstract roles of stakeholders that are involved in MPM4CPS can be fully specified.

A complete set of characteristics can be distilled that is suitable for expressively specifying all respective stakeholders.

The roles of stakeholders can be unambiguously assigned to specific stages of MPM4CPS-lifecycles.

3.2 Survey Development

Adhering to the line of reasoning mapped out above, we generate tables based on which it is possible to deduce several concrete surveys we plan to execute coming year.

Abbreviations: Types: SC: Single Choice; MC: Multiple Choice; FT: Free Text; LS: Likert-Scale (1=No agreement to 5=Agreement)

Nr.	Category	Question	Answers	Question Type
1	Metadata	What is the size of your company (CPS and other areas)?		SC
			1-10 employees	
			11-50 employees	
			51-250 employees	
			251-500 employees	
			501-1000 employees	
			1001-2000 employees	
2	Metadata	Please briefly describe the main sector of your company and the application domain of the CPS you build.		FT
3	Metadata	Does your company participate in globally distributed CPS projects?		SC
			yes	
			no	
4	Metadata	In case your company participates in globally distributed CPS projects, in which country are you personally located?		FT
5	Metadata	To which CPS project role are you most frequently assigned to in those CPS projects?		SC
			Business Analyst	
			Requirements Engineer	
			Project Lead / Project Manager	
			Test Manager / Tester	
			Architect	
			Developer	
Other	FT			
6	Metadata	How do you rate your experience in this role?		SC
			Novice (up to 1 year experience)	
			Experienced (1-3 years experience)	
			Expert (more than 3 years experience)	
7	Metadata	Which organisational role does your company take most frequently in your CPS projects?		MC
			Customer	
			Product development	
			Contractor	
			Other	FT
9	Status Quo in CPS Requirements Engineering	How do you elicit CPS requirements?		MC
			Interviews	
			Scenarios	
			Prototyping	
			Facilitated meetings (including workshops)	
			Observation	
Other	FT			

Table 1: Meta-data survey questions.

Abbreviations: Types: SC: Single Choice; MC: Multiple Choice; FT: Free Text; LS: Likert-Scale (1=No agreement to 5=Agreement)

Nr.	Category	Question	Answers	Question Type
10	The influence of MPM at respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle	What are the typical lifecycle stages in real-life CPS projects?		FT
11	The influence of MPM at respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle	What are the respective modeling paradigms considered in CPS projects?	Waterfall V-Modell XT Scrum Architecture centric Embedded-system centric Other	MC FT
12	The influence of MPM at respective stages of a CPS-development lifecycle	What paradigms affect respective lifecycle stages in a CPS project?		FT
13	Key criteria to measure the benefits of MPM4CPS	What criteria measure MPM-utility in a CPS project?	interoperability formalization expressiveness semantics modeling language syntax modeling language others	MC FT
14	Key criteria to measure the benefits of MPM4CPS	What criteria measure MPM-efficiency (time&money) in a CPS project?	interoperability formalization expressiveness semantics modeling language syntax modeling language others	MC FT
15	Key criteria to measure the benefits of MPM4CPS	What is the perceived quality improvement by MPM4CPS?		FT
16	Detect the roles that diverse stakeholders play at different stages of an MPM4CPS development lifecycle	What stakeholder roles exist in MPM4CPS?	Engineer CXO Project Lead / Project Manager customer other	MC / FT
17	Detect the roles that diverse stakeholders play at different stages of an MPM4CPS development lifecycle	What are the characteristics of those respective stakeholder roles?	Engineer CXO Project Lead / Project Manager customer other	FT
18	Detect the roles that diverse stakeholders play at different stages of an MPM4CPS development lifecycle	Which stakeholder roles is involved in which stage of an MPM4CPS development lifecycle?	Engineer CXO Project Lead / Project Manager customer other	FT

Table 2: Main survey questions that match the drafted paper.

The next survey questions are randomly generated, do not match with the hypothesis of the drafted paper and are input for future survey-based research.

19	Artefacts used and the purpose of using them during the development of CPS	Which development processes do you use?
20	Artefacts used and the purpose of using them during the development of CPS	What are the modelling artefacts used in CPS projects?
21	Artefacts used and the purpose of using them during the development of CPS	What's the purpose of using these modeling artefacts?
22	Measure the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling with key criteria	Which are the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling?
23	Measure the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling with key criteria	Which are the key criteria for measuring the benefits?
24	Measure the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling with key criteria	What is the perceived benefits in using MPM?
25	Different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS, and what are their concerns?	Which are the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS?
26	Different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS, and what are their concerns?	Which are the concerns of the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS?

Table 3: Randomly generated questions for future survey design.

4 Survey Beta-Version

The tables above are input for deducing a beta-version of a concrete survey we plan to execute and scholarly publish about in 2017. This survey-version below must first go through a testing phase with a small focus group. The alpha version we plan to release with an online survey tool for a pan-European focus group.

4.1 Research Questions

RQ1: Which artefacts are used and what is the purpose of using them during the development of CPS?

RQ 1.1: What development processes do you use?

RQ 1.2: According to your experience, what are the artefacts used in your CPS projects?

RQ 1.3: What is the purpose of using these modelling artefacts?

RQ2: Is there a way to measure the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling, and what are the key criteria for measuring the benefits?

RQ 2.1: What are the benefits of multi-paradigm modelling and the key criteria for measuring them?

RQ 2.2: What are the perceived benefits in using MPM?

RQ3: Which are the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS, and what are their concerns?

RQ 3.1: Which are the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS?

RQ 3.2: Which are the concerns of the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS?

RQ4: Is there space for improvement on, e.g. (i) integrating artefacts related to different paradigms (ii) improving knowledge sharing and communication among stakeholders involved in different paradigms?

RQ 4.1: Do you have suggestions for cross-paradigm improvements?

RQ 4.2: Do you have suggestions for improvements within one paradigm that can affect the MPM?

4.2 Specific questions composing the survey

4.2.1 Context

1. In which company do you work?
 - a. Free text
2. In which domain does your company work?
 - a. Multiple choice
3. What is your company's position in the value chain?
 - a. Multiple choice
4. Is your company a Small or Medium Enterprise (SME, ≤ 250 employees) or a large company (or part of)?
 - a. Yes/no
5. In which division/department do you work?
 - a. Free text
6. To which paradigm is related your division/department?
 - a. Multiple choice
7. What are the main working tasks related to your role?
 - a. Multiple choice (specific of the domain)
8. Is your company using models, such as UML models, domain specific models, both formal and informal also and for how long?
 - a. Multiple choice
9. Do you see yourself as a promoter or opponent of of multi-paradigm modelling?
10. Are you involved in modelling within you company? If so, is your involvement related to multi-paradigm modelling?
11. Which standards does your company apply that relate to the modelling strategy of your company?
 - a. Free text (provide examples)
12. Please rate your experience with modelling.

- a. 5-value Likert scale

13. What kind of CPSs does your company develop?

- a. Free text

4.2.2 RQ1-related questions

1. What is the development process used in your division/department?

- a. Multiple choice with other (free text) at the end

2. Please list the different types of artifacts used in your division/department?

- a. Free text

3. Do you use them for software, hardware, mechanics, etc. ?

- a. Multiple choice (enable multiple selections)

4. What is the purpose of the artefacts used in your division/department?

- a. Multiple choice: communication, code generation, model-based testing, early analysis, verification, ...

5. Who are the consumers of these artefacts?

- a. Free text, provide examples spanning among the stakeholders in the MPM

6. What is the life cycle of these artefacts?

- a. Multiple choice: continuously updated, defined ones once and trashed, defined and never updated, ...

7. What tools/modelling environments are used in your division/department?

- a. Free text

8. Which type(s) of notations are used in your division/department?

- a. Free text

9. Do you have the need for combining different modelling approaches in your CPS development process?

- a. Yes/no

10. What is your specific need for combining different modelling approaches in your CPS development process?
 - a. Free text (provide examples)
11. What's the strategy you follow for combining different modelling approaches in your CPS development process?
 - a. Free text
12. Can you cover all the perceived needs in your CPS development process?
 - a. Yes/no
13. If not, what are you missing?
 - a. Free text
14. Which type(s) of integration mechanisms among artifacts are used in your division/department?
 - a. Free text

4.2.3 RQ2-related questions

1. What are the main benefits of using multi-paradigm modelling in CPS development?
 - a. Multiple-choice: time-saving, performance, quality, ...
2. Do you have metrics for measuring the benefits that the multi-paradigm modelling adoption yields in CPS development?
 - a. Yes/no
3. If no, do you think that having such metrics would have a value?
 - a. Yes/no
4. If no, how do you measure the benefits of your projects that use multi-paradigm modelling?
 - a. Free text
5. If yes, what do these metrics measure exactly?
 - a. Free text

6. If yes, which are the criteria for measuring the benefits of using multi-paradigm modelling in CPS development?
 - a. Free text
7. If yes, are you happy with these metrics or would it be important to ameliorate them?
 - a. Yes/no
8. In general, what are the perceived benefits of using multi-paradigm modelling in CPS development?
9. During the CPS modeling, what trade-offs among quality parameters do you experience? Please give examples.
 - a. Free text

4.2.4 RQ3-related questions

1. Please list the different stakeholders involved in the development of a CPS.
 - o Free text
2. Does your organization understand what characteristics describe the respective roles you are aware of?
 - o Yes/no
3. Do the different stakeholders have different concerns?
 - o Yes/no
4. If yes, might you please provide examples?
 - o Free text
5. Do you see conflicting concerns among the different stakeholders?
 - o Yes/no
6. If yes, might you please provide examples?
 - o Free text

7. How do the different stakeholders communicate with each other?
 - o Multiple choice: Documentation-based communication, meetings, workshops, mix of communication means, etc.

4.2.5 RQ4-related questions

1. Do you see any Return On Investment (ROI) in improving the multi-paradigm modelling methods in your division/department?
 - a. Yes/no
2. What are the improvements you would like to see?
 - a. Free text
3. Do you think that it might be of value to ameliorate the integration between artefacts related to different paradigms?
 - a. Yes/no
4. If yes, do you have any idea on how this might improve?
 - a. Free text
5. If no, might you please explain why?
 - a. Free text
6. Do you think that the knowledge sharing among different stakeholders should improve?
 - a. Yes/no
7. If yes, do you have any idea on how this might improve?
 - a. Free text
8. If no, might you please explain why?
 - a. Free text
9. Do you think that the communication among different stakeholders should improve?
 - a. Yes/no

10. If yes, do you have any idea on how this might improve?

a. Free text

11. If no, might you please explain why?

a. Free text

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